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TikTok Operations in the United States

Unveiling Strategic Moves, Scientific Insights and What Lies Ahead

Synopsis

On 24 April 2024 President Biden signed a Bill to force the divestment of ByteDance in TikTok's American legal entity. Biden and the Bill's many supporters cited national security concerns and accusations that TikTok is effectively an influence operations capability of the Chinese government. Current analysis on the nature of TikTok operations in the United States (and elsewhere) has focused heavily on comparative content analysis where content that is pushed to American users is compared to what content is pushed to Chinese users on domestic platforms such as *Douyan* (抖音). While comparative content analysis methods do have merit, there remains a substantial degree of subjectivity and a lack of consistent analytical techniques. This Background Brief has surfaced multiple recent scientific studies conducted in China that are relevant to TikTok, including at the Party School of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China. Relevant People's Liberation Army (PLA) doctrinal publications are also analyzed and assessed. These primary sources provide a rare direct view into the fundamental strategic and technical underpinnings of a platform such as TikTok that are used in the United States to influence public opinion. This report concludes with a section of implications and likely new approaches by Beijing to attempt to maintain its presence inside in the United States in the information operations domain.

Executive Summary

1. **Presidential Action on TikTok:** On 24 April 2024, President Biden signed a Bill mandating that ByteDance must divest from TikTok's U.S. operations. ByteDance has vowed to challenge the bill in the American legal system.
2. **Bipartisan Support and Public Opinion:** The decision to sign the bill received broad bipartisan support in the United States Congress. However, American public opinion, especially amongst the 18–34-year-old demographic, remains split.
3. **Chinese Government Linkages:** The action followed extensive investigations and intelligence briefings, which claimed that TikTok was acting as an extension of Beijing's influence operations and could serve strategic Chinese interests within the United States.
4. **Influence Operations Concerns:** There is a growing concern about China's potential use of TikTok for information and psychological operations within the U.S. to sway public opinion on key issues like Taiwan and the perceived shortfalls of the American form of democracy.
5. **Strategic Communication Tactics:** The utilization of America's own cultural constructs and communication preferences is emphasized as a method for effectively disseminating Chinese narratives via platforms like TikTok.
6. **Legal and Civil Rights Challenges:** The Bill faces opposition from several U.S. groups, including the American Civil Liberties Union (ACLU), highlighting the complexities and legal challenges associated with enforcing such a divestment.
7. **Beijing's Response:** Possibly in anticipation of adverse action being taken against TikTok in the United States, Beijing appears to be targeting American platforms such as YouTube and other American news and social media sites. This pivot is indicative of a broader, more embedded approach aimed at influencing American narratives and strengthening China's communication capabilities within the United States.
8. **Three Warfares Strategy:** In 2014, China's National Defense University published the 'Three Warfares' strategy, which emphasizes psychological, media and legal warfare to achieve strategic objectives traditionally pursued through conventional military means.
9. **Potential Civil-Military Fusion:** There appears to be considerable convergence between overt PLA doctrine on information warfare that was published in 2015, 2014, 2013 and 1995, the founding of TikTok in 2016 and subsequent Chinese scientific advances in the strategic types of influence operations used by TikTok in 2023.
10. **American Case Study:** The overlap between the Three Warfares doctrine and TikTok's observed operations and techniques in the United States is perhaps the most noteworthy of all.

Biden Signs the Forced Divestment Bill: Bipartisanship in Congress with American Public Opinion Split

- 1.1 On 24 April 2024 President Biden signed a Bill requiring ByteDance to divest from the American legal entity of TikTok, a Chinese video sharing platform that was founded in September 2016, on national security grounds. This Bill represented a rare example of bipartisan cooperation in the United States Congress. ByteDance has vowed to challenge President Biden's decision in court arguing that this Bill violates the company's First Amendment rights.¹ China is also likely to retaliate against the United States over this action. However, it is unclear what immediate actions will be taken due to the minimal presence of American social media companies in China.
- 1.2 American public opinion data reveals a more divided national view, especially amongst the 18-34-year old demographic that is the most intense users of TikTok. Amongst this demographic, only 48% are against this forced divestment while only 58% of the general population views TikTok as an information operation on the Chinese government. TikTok is currently believed to have 170 million registered users in the United States.² However, most Americans appear to accept a continued presence of TikTok inside the country if it is divested of Chinese ownership. This presents a potential window of opportunity for TikTok to remain a key feature of the social media environment in the United States.
- 1.3 For some of the younger TikTok users in the United States, this Bill may actually become a core election issue given their heavy use of the platform. Some of these voters are traditionally more inclined to vote for the Democratic Party but this issue could fuse together with complaints regarding the Biden Administration's continuous supply of weapons and ammunition to Israel to prosecute its ongoing war against Hamas.
- 1.4 This Presidential action was preceded by months of investigations and media reporting on the linkages between TikTok and the Chinese government and accusations that TikTok operates as an extension of Beijing. This process culminated

¹ Lauren Feiner, 'Biden signs TikTok 'ban' bill into law, starting the clock for ByteDance to divest it', The Verge, 24 April 2024.

[Biden signs TikTok 'ban' bill into law, starting the clock for ByteDance to divest it - The Verge](#), accessed on 3 May 2024.

Angela Yang and Savannah Sellers, 'TikTok sues U.S. government, saying potential ban violates First Amendment', *NBC News*, 8 May 2024.

[TikTok sues U.S. government, saying potential ban violates First Amendment \(nbcnews.com\)](#), accessed on 8 May 2024.

'TikTok to challenge US ban Bill in court after Biden signs it into law', *Straits Times*, 25 April 2024.

[TikTok to challenge US ban Bill in court after Biden signs it into law | The Straits Times](#), accessed on 5 May 2024.

² Steve Liesman and Zach Vallese, 'Close to half of Americans back a ban or sale of TikTok, CNBC survey found', *CNBC*, 27 March 2024.

[Close to half of Americans back a ban or sale of TikTok, CNBC survey found](#), accessed on 14 May 2024.

Jason Lange and David Shepardson, 'Most Americans see TikTok as a Chinese influence tool, Reuters/Ipsos poll finds', *Reuters*, 1 May 2024.

[Most Americans see TikTok as a Chinese influence tool, Reuters/Ipsos poll finds | Reuters](#), accessed on 5 May 2024.

in a still-classified briefing on 20 March when senior U.S. intelligence officials provided their evidence against TikTok to senior U.S. Senators.³

- 1.5 This Bill should also be considered within the context of the November 2022 decision by President Biden to ban the Chinese companies of Huawei, ZTE, Hikvision, Dahua and Hytera on national security grounds.⁴ This type of American action against TikTok is not unprecedented.
- 1.6 This Bill also represents part of a broader trend of China-U.S. decoupling that began under the Trump Administration. China and the United States are in the process of decoupling in trade, human talent, financial services and technology though both countries still remain key trading partners and have common interests to address climate change.
- 1.7 However, given the strategic nature of TikTok due to its demonstrated influence capability in the United States, this Bill could further accelerate the decoupling process. The negative consequences could also spill over into the last remaining areas of cooperation. Beijing may claim that this is yet another example of American discrimination against China's technology sector. On the other hand, Washington may cite TikTok as another source of evidence of China's unrelenting effort to unduly influence American domestic public opinion and even voter behaviour.
- 1.8 The TikTok case forms part of a broader American concern regarding Chinese information and psychological operations inside the United States to actively shape public opinion in favor of Beijing's positions on matters such as Taiwan, Hamas-Israel and Beijing's criticisms of the American form of democracy. Even if ByteDance is eventually forced to divest from TikTok, these concerns will likely remain in some form. However, these American concerns will have to then factor in the new ownership and management structure as well as TikTok's consistently strong user base.
- 1.9 There is also well-established PLA literature and other Chinese research works on the utility of psychological operations to achieve strategic objectives against a

³ David Shephardson, 'US officials to brief senators Wednesday on threats posed by TikTok, aide says', Reuters, 19 March 2024.

[US officials to brief senators Wednesday on threats posed by TikTok, aide says | Reuters](#), accessed on 5 May 2024.

⁴ Kenji Kawase, 'Sanctioned Chinese security camera maker Dahua divests from U.S.', *Nikkei Asia*, 17 April 2024.

[Sanctioned Chinese security camera maker Dahua divests from U.S. - Nikkei Asia](#)

Diane Bartz and Alexandra Alper, 'U.S. bans new Huawei, ZTE equipment sales, citing national security risk', *Reuters*, 1 December 2022.

[U.S. bans new Huawei, ZTE equipment sales, citing national security risk | Reuters](#), accessed on 14 May 2024.

Carly Page, 'US government bans Huawei, ZTE and Hikvision tech over 'unacceptable' spying fears', *TechCrunch*, 28 November 2022.

[US government bans Huawei, ZTE and Hikvision tech over 'unacceptable' spying fears | TechCrunch](#), accessed on 14 May 2024.

conventionally superior adversary.⁵ American analysts and policymakers are increasingly referencing this body of work.⁶

- 1.10 In 2014, China's National Defense University fully articulated the 'Three Warfares' (三种战法) strategic concept. Three Warfares is specifically designed to enable China to achieve end goals that have traditionally been accomplished by conventional military force through the effective use of psychological warfare, media warfare and legal warfare.
- 1.11 The Three Warfares is intended to be integrated across the entire spectrum of military operations. Functions have also expanded and correspond to the PLA's increasing range of military missions. Core functions include, but are not limited to:
- Control of public opinion (舆论控制)
 - Blunting an adversary's determination (意志挫伤)
 - Transformation of emotion (情感转化)
 - Psychological guidance (心智诱导)
 - Collapse of (an adversary's) organization (组织瓦解)
 - Psychological defense (心理防御)
 - Restriction through law (法律制约)⁷

⁵ For example, see Tianliang Xiao [肖天亮], eds., *The Science of Military Strategy* [战略学]. PLA National Defence University Press, Beijing, 2015.

Jieming Wu [吴杰明] and Zhifu Liu [刘志富], *An Introduction to Public Opinion Warfare, Psychological Warfare, [and] Legal Warfare* [舆论战心理战法律战概论], PLA National Defence University Press, Beijing, 2014.

Academy of Military Science Military Strategy Research Department [军事科学院军事战略研究部], eds., *The Science of Military Strategy* [战略学]. Military Science Press, Beijing, 2013.

Qiao Liang (乔良) and Wang Xiangsui (王湘穗), *Unrestricted Warfare* [超限战], PLA Literature and Publishing House, Beijing, 1999.

Baocun Wang and Fei Li, "Information Warfare," *Liberation Army Daily by Federation of American Scientists*, June 1995.

⁶ For example, see Robert Spalding, *War Without Rules: China's Playbook for Global Domination*, Sentinel, 22 April 2022.

Kerry Gershanek, *Political Warfare: Strategies for Combatting China's Plan to "Win without Fighting"*, Marine Corps University Press, 2020.

Robert Spalding, *Stealth War: How China Took Over While America's Elite Slept*, Penguin Random House, 1 October 2019.

Michael Clarke, "China's Application of the 'Three Warfares' in the South China Sea and Xinjiang", *Orbis*, January 2019.

Matthew Brazil and Peter Mattis, *Chinese Communist Espionage: An Intelligence Primer*, Naval Institute Press, 2019.

Doug Livermore, "China's 'Three Warfares' In Theory and Practice in the South China Sea", *Georgetown Security Studies Review*, 25 March 2018.

Jason Fritz, *China's Cyber Warfare: The Evolution of Strategic Doctrine*, Lexington Books, 2017.

Elsa Kania, "The PLA's Latest Strategic Thinking on the Three Warfares", *China Brief*, Vol. 16, Iss. 13, 22 August 2016.

United States Department of Defence, "Annual Report to Congress: Military and Security Developments Involving the People's Republic of China 2011", 2011.

⁷ Elsa Kania, "The PLA's Latest Strategic Thinking on the Three Warfares", *China Brief*, Vol. 16, Iss. 13, 22 August 2016.

- 1.12 In broader strategic terms, the primary missions are to seize the ‘decisive opportunity’ (先机) for controlling public opinion, organizing psychological offense and defense, engaging in legal struggle and fighting for popular will and public opinion.⁸ Under this combined framework, China must simultaneously unify military and civilian thinking, divide an enemy into factions, weaken the enemy’s combat power and organize legal offensives.⁹
- 1.13 It is noteworthy that several of the legal challenges that this Bill is facing are already coming from American groups themselves, including the ACLU.¹⁰

Potential Risks of United Front Infiltration in the United States

- 2.1 One key area of concern is the use of TikTok by China’s United Front, which is also under increasing scrutiny inside the United States, especially as it pertains to protecting the rights and liberties of people of Chinese descent residing in the country.
- 2.2 There is an active research agenda within China on how to psychologically separate American citizens and residents of Chinese descent and dilute their focus on their American identity in favor of a Chinese one. There is additional research being done on how to accomplish this through the use of short videos that are remarkably similar to those used by TikTok.¹¹
- 2.3 There are also data privacy and surveillance concerns. The United Front has demonstrated its involvement in targeting overseas Chinese communities.¹² There is a risk that TikTok could be used to gather intelligence on overseas Chinese and intellectuals under the guise of community and cultural engagement initiatives.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ ACLU Statement on Congress’ Latest Attempt to Ban TikTok and Restrict Free Speech Online, Press Release, American Civil Liberties Union, 23 April 2024.

[ACLU Statement on Congress’ Latest Attempt to Ban TikTok and Restrict Free Speech Online | American Civil Liberties Union](#), accessed 5 May 2024.

¹¹ Wu Chao, ‘Training pathways for the new generation of overseas Chinese based on dual cultural identity theory’ [基于双重文化认同理论的海外华裔新生代培养路径], *Education Review* [教育评论], Issue 7, 29 October 2023.

Cao Yuejuan., Huang Chuxin and Liang, Zishan, ‘Pathways to enhance overseas recognition of China's image through short videos’ [利用短视频提高海外对中国形象认同的路径], *New Observation on Media Convergence* [媒体融合新观察], 6 August 2023.

¹² Joint address by MI5 and FBI Heads, News and Speeches, MI5, London/Washington DC, 6 July 2022.

[Joint address by MI5 and FBI Heads | MI5 - The Security Service](#), accessed on 5 May 2024.

Bethany Allen-Ebrahimian, ‘DOJ indictment alleges China's United Front involvement in repression’, *Axios*, 16 May 2023.

[DOJ indictment alleges China's United Front involvement in repression \(axios.com\)](#), accessed on 5 May 2023.

- 2.4 Recent research in China highlights how short videos can effectively shape public opinion and improve overseas recognition of China's image.¹³ TikTok's control over a major global short video platform with a strong American user base could be leveraged to promote content that subtly aligns with Chinese political interests and ideologies. This can include narratives that promote the Chinese government's perspective on international matters or suppress dissenting views, which poses a risk to the informational integrity and autonomy of users in the United States.

Concerns Over Targeting of Intellectuals Inside the United States

- 3.1 There are growing concerns inside the United States that TikTok represents a strategic use of media to target intellectuals and the diaspora, focusing on aligning their views with Beijing's objectives and thereby reducing intellectual freedom inside the United States.
- 3.2 There are also concerns that TikTok could engage in similar practices in Allied countries, where the company's platforms might be used to monitor, profile and influence American/Allied intellectuals and critics of the Chinese government. This could be achieved through tailored content curation that either promotes pro-Beijing narratives or marginalizes critical voices.
- 3.3 China sees short videos as a powerful tool for international communication to enhance its image in the domestic United States. TikTok could be instrumental in these efforts, pushing content that enhances the perception of China, while downplaying or omitting issues that are sensitive to Beijing. This could skew public perception and debate in the United States, including geographies where a significant portion of the population is of Chinese descent.
- 3.4 The potential for misuse of the TikTok platforms to disseminate strategic misinformation or selectively highlight information to benefit China's image is a significant risk. This could be particularly impactful in times of geopolitical tension, where nuanced manipulation of video content could sway public opinion or cause confusion.

Strategic Communication and Ideological Influence

- 4.1 A 2023 report was produced by Zhang Gaifeng of the School of Marxism at the Hefei University of Technology that was funded by the Chinese government as a futures project. This report, titled '**Grasp the variables, stocks and increments of mainstream ideological discourse innovation in the new era**', emphasizes the

¹³ Cao Yuejuan., Huang Chuxin and Liang, Zishan, 'Pathways to enhance overseas recognition of China's image through short videos' [利用短视频提高海外对中国形象认同的路径], *New Observation on Media Convergence* [媒体融合新观察], 6 August 2023.

Beijing's focus on enhancing China's discourse power globally by leveraging cultural and ideological narratives.¹⁴

- 4.2 TikTok, operating within this ideological framework, could be directly utilized to incorporate and disseminate content that aligns with these strategic objectives. This includes the promotion of concepts such as 'Chinese-style modernization' and the 'Chinese Dream', which are central to Beijing's ideological engagement strategy.¹⁵
- 4.3 Zhang's report discusses the need for China to seize 'variable opportunities' in the information environment to innovate on its mainstream ideological discourse.¹⁶ This suggests a dynamic and evolving approach to adjusting and reforming narratives based on American perceptions and Washington's stance towards China. For TikTok, this could translate into a tailored approach where content is curated or suppressed based on strategic ideological priorities from Beijing, potentially manipulating public opinion inside the United States and possibly Allied countries.
- 4.4 The emphasis on incremental dissemination and the use of new forms and concepts to expand the discourse across the United States could manifest through the TikTok American platform. By promoting ideologically charged content subtly and incrementally, TikTok could facilitate a gradual shift in perceptions, aligning more closely with Chinese ideological stances without overt censorship or propaganda.
- 4.5 Zhang finally highlights the cultivation of youth to promote ideological narratives, recognizing the potential of younger generations to advance and normalize these narratives through new media forms. TikTok, with its significant youth user base, presents a potent tool for engaging with and shaping the ideologies of younger American demographics. This would ensure the continuity and adaptation of China's ideological influence among future generations.
- 4.6 According to another 2022 study by Hu Liang-quan from the Propaganda and Traditional Warfare Department of Hunan University, TikTok's characteristics as a short video platform (broad audience, vivid imagery and rich content) are ideally suited for the ideological and political education of college students. The study, titled '**The application and enlightenment of TikTok in ideological and political education for college students**', explores how TikTok can expand the channels and ways of delivering ideological and political education, taking full advantage of the

¹⁴ Zhang Gaifeng, 'Grasp the variables, stocks, and increments of mainstream ideological discourse innovation in the new era' [把握新时代主流意识形态话语创新的变量、存量与增量], *Ideological and Political Education Research* [思想政治教育研究], 4 September 2023.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

platform's reach and appeal amongs younger users (those born in the 1990s) to influence this key demographic.¹⁷

Utilizing America's Own Cultural Constructs to Obtain Strategic Influence

- 5.1 Beijing has been strategic in its use of media to project its image and ideology across the world, particularly leveraging constructs that resonate well with specific cultural and regional demographics. American anthropologist Edward T. Hall's concept of 'high- and low-context cultures' provides a critical framework through which the Beijing's tactics can be analyzed and understood. Hall's framework is of particular interest to Chinese researchers working in the influence field.¹⁸
- 5.2 In American and other Western societies, which Hall categorizes as 'low-context cultures'¹⁹, communication tends to be direct, explicit and heavily reliant on explicit verbal messages. Understanding this cultural preference, Beijing appears to use platforms like TikTok to engage with these audiences through clear, engaging and straightforward messages often embedded within entertainment.
- 5.3 This method cleverly complements the Western preference for clear and unambiguous communication, which helps reduce the cultural discount typically associated with foreign messages, making the content more relatable and effective.
- 5.4 Short video formats used on platforms like TikTok also naturally align with the Western communication style by providing quick, clear and highly interactive content. This form of media allows for rapid dissemination and high levels of user engagement through likes, shares and comments thus enhancing the spread and acceptance of tailored messages that subtly promote China's cultural and political narratives.

What is Beijing's Post-TikTok Strategy? Evidence from the Central Committee Party School

- 6.1 Possibly in anticipation of adverse action being taken against TikTok in the United States, Beijing appears to be targeting American platforms such as and other American news and social media sites to enhance their United Front work. This pivot is indicative of a broader, more embedded approach aimed at influencing American narratives and strengthening China's communication capabilities within the United States.

¹⁷ Hu Liang-quan, 'The application and enlightenment of TikTok in ideological and political education for college students' [抖音在大学生思想政治教育工作中的应用及启示], *China Journal of Multimedia & Network Teaching* [中国多媒体与网络教学学报], 01 January 2022.

¹⁸ Edwin T. Hall, *Beyond Culture*, Doubleday, New York, 1989.
Cao Yuejuan., Huang Chuxin and Liang, Zishan, 'Pathways to enhance overseas recognition of China's image through short videos' [利用短视频提高海外对中国形象认同的路径], *New Observation on Media Convergence* [媒体融合新观察], 6 August 2023.

¹⁹ Edwin T. Hall, *Beyond Culture*, Doubleday, New York, 1989.

- 6.2 In 2023 Qu Pengfei, of the Institute of International Strategy, Party School of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China, reveals a calculated expansion into platforms that are deeply integrated into American media consumption habits, namely YouTube.²⁰ YouTube, with its vast American (and global) reach, offers a potent medium for disseminating the Chinese narrative to a broader American audience.
- 6.3 Qu notes that the YouTube platform facilitates a deeper penetration of Beijing's messages due to its already-established credibility and extensive user base that spans across diverse demographics and geographical boundaries within the United States.²¹
- 6.4 YouTube's algorithmic nature, which pushes content based on user preference rather than geopolitical origin, allows for the subtle integration of content aligned with China's strategic interests. This method is particularly effective in low-context cultures, like the United States, where direct and clear communication is preferred. By tailoring content to these cultural preferences, Beijing can craft messages that resonate more deeply with target audiences, thereby improving the effectiveness of its American voice.
- 6.5 In addition to Beijing's diversification strategy into other American social media platforms to maintain its position, in the future China may also attempt to re-engage with TikTok using a range of financial techniques. One such technique could be the use of an American (or Allied) fund, in which a Beijing-linked entity is a Limited Partner and investor, to acquire a material amount of shares in the post-ByteDance, American TikTok. If the shareholding rises above a certain percentage threshold, it could provide for shareholder rights that would enable Beijing to still retain some strategic influence and control over the company, albeit through more indirect means.

Assessment and Implications

- 7.1 The strategic utilization of the TikTok platform inside the United States, particularly in light of the insights from these identified reports, underscores significant risks to the intellectual freedom, privacy and information integrity within America's digital landscape.
- 7.2 These risks are manifold, encompassing potential breaches of data privacy, the surveillance of users, manipulation of content and the systematic promotion of specific political narratives aligned with the interests of Beijing.
- 7.3 Such activities are informed by tactics discussed in China's own scientific literature on the use of media for ideological influence and the strategic deployment of cultural and political narratives to shape public perception and discourse.

²⁰ Qu Pengfei, 'The Connotation and Path of Improving China's International Communication Capabilities in the New Era' [新时代提升中国国际传播能力的内涵与路径], *Journal of China Jinggangshan Cadre College* [中国井冈山干部学院学报], 12 January 2023.

²¹ Ibid.

- 7.4 The analysis derived from Zhang Gaifeng's discussion on the innovation of China's mainstream ideological discourse reveals an additional layer of risk. It highlights a deliberate strategy to innovate and adapt ideological content to influence American audiences subtly.
- 7.5 The TikTok American platform could serve as a conduit for this influence, leveraging its technological capabilities and vast user engagement to shift American narratives subtly to favor a more China-centric worldview. This is not just a direct imposition of propaganda but a more nuanced approach to shaping perceptions and cultural attitudes over time. This approach can potentially normalize viewpoints that align with Chinese interests among young, impressionable audiences in America.
- 7.6 There appears to be considerable convergence between overt PLA doctrine on information warfare that was published in 2015 (Three Warfares), 2014, 2013, 1999 and 1995, the founding of TikTok in 2016 and subsequent Chinese scientific advances in the strategic types of influence operations used by TikTok in 2023. The overlap between the Three Warfares doctrine and TikTok's observed operations and techniques in the United States is perhaps the most noteworthy of all.
- 7.7 This Bill will likely result in Chinese retaliation coupled with accusations of unfounded American hostility towards China's technology sector. This has the potential to further accelerate the ongoing decoupling process in areas such as trade, financial services, human talent and the technology sector that began under the Trump Administration. It also has the potential to destabilize the last few shared interests between Beijing and Washington, such as cooperation to address and respond to climate change.
- 7.8 This Bill is not likely to be implemented over the near-term as ByteDance will utilize all legal options to challenge President Biden's decision. During this period, TikTok will likely continue to operate as it has been in the United States. Even in the event of an eventual forced ByteDance divestment of TikTok, it is unclear if Beijing will relinquish this hard-earned asset or if Beijing will attempt to reinsert itself into TikTok's new American structure through other indirect means.